

1 **Introducing an Integration Approach Combining the Client-Oriented Scale of**
2 **Improvement (COSI) With Ecological Momentary Assessment for Evaluating**
3 **Real-World Listening Challenges and Hearing-Aid Benefits; a feasibility**
4 **study**

5

6 **Corresponding author:** Tahereh Afghah

7 tafghah@hz-ol.de

8

9 Tahereh Afghah^{1,2}, Petra von Gablenz³, Sven Franz³, Ulrik Kowalk³, Inga Holube^{2,3}, and Kirsten
10 C. Wagener^{1,2}

11 ¹Hörzentrum Oldenburg gGmbH, Oldenburg, Germany

12 ²Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Oldenburg, Germany

13 ³Institute of Hearing Technology and Audiology, Jade University of Applied Sciences,
14 Oldenburg, Germany

15 **Keywords:** Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA); Hearing impairment; Patient-centered
16 care, Patient-Reported Outcomes (PRO); Personalized Intervention; Hearing aid benefit; Client-
17 Oriented Scale of Improvement (COSI)

18 **Conflict of Interest:** There are no conflicts of interest.

19 Abstract

20 **Purpose:** Traditional hearing assessments often do not reflect the complex listening environments
21 in everyday life. It is essential to capture listening difficulties and characterize hearing aids benefits
22 in daily contexts. This study proposed and evaluated the feasibility and applicability of an approach
23 integrating the Client-Oriented Scale of Improvement (COSI) with Ecological Momentary
24 Assessment (EMA) to assess hearing difficulties and hearing aid benefits in individually defined
25 challenging everyday situations, with the aim of informing its development as an assessment tool.

26 **Method:** Twenty participants, including normal-hearing and hearing-impaired individuals without
27 hearing aids, and hearing aid users were examined. A two-phase experiment was conducted using
28 two questionnaires adapted from COSI and implemented through the olMEGA app. Phase 1: All
29 participants completed the first EMA questionnaire whenever they experienced listening
30 impairment at home, on the way, in social settings, and at work, over one week. The non-user
31 group was fitted with hearing aids and used them for 5-6 weeks. Phase 2: For this group, up to five
32 individually assigned EMA-based listening environments, were reproduced and participants
33 revisited these environments and completed the second EMA questionnaire while wearing hearing
34 aids over one week. **Results:** Phase 1: Conversation-based listening situations and media listening
35 were most often reported as challenging. Hearing-impaired participants reported greater listening
36 effort, concentration difficulty, perceived impairment, and poorer speech understanding and
37 localization than normal-hearing participants. Phase 1 vs. 2: Changes in perceived impairment,
38 listening effort, concentration difficulty, speech comprehension, sound pleasantness, and
39 localization were observed within this limited sample, which illustrates its potential applicability
40 for reflecting perceived hearing aid benefits. **Conclusions:** The COSI-EMA questionnaire and
41 two-phase design demonstrated the feasibility of identifying challenging listening situations and

42 illustrating hearing-aid benefits with high ecological validity. Adequate usability and technical
43 stability of the EMA system is essential to fully realize the potential of this approach in routine
44 applications.

45

46 **1. Introduction**

47 Hearing impairment is a growing public health concern, affecting the lives of over 1.5 billion
48 people worldwide who experience some degree of hearing loss (HL) (WHO, 2021). To effectively
49 address this public health issue, it is essential to develop HL evaluation methodologies that assess
50 hearing loss in the context of the real-world listening challenges individuals face. HL assessment
51 is traditionally conducted in laboratory-based settings, such as acoustically treated sound booths,
52 with minimal reflections from surfaces, interfering sounds, or external noise. However, in
53 everyday listening situations, individuals must segregate the sound of interest from other existing
54 sounds in the auditory scene. As the presence of multiple simultaneous sounds highly increases
55 the listening task complexity, commonly referred to as the "Cocktail party effect" (Cherry, 1953),
56 the hearing difficulties in such situations cannot be accurately represented by those measured in
57 quiet, acoustically controlled spaces.

58 To bridge this gap and perform a patient-centered hearing loss evaluation and intervention,
59 several approaches have been proposed. 1) Self-report measures: questionnaires or interviews that
60 inquire about perceived listening challenges in variety of proposed sample listening situations; 2)
61 Real-time data collection: Gathering information while individuals experience daily listening
62 situations; 3) Laboratory simulations: controlled experiments conducted to virtually reproduce
63 real-life acoustic scenarios.

64 In the **first** approach, listening challenges are identified retrospectively through interviews
65 or using validated questionnaires filled out retrospectively. Patients may be asked to respond to
66 questions about their everyday listening experiences over the past four weeks. This method is
67 advantageous, as it allows the healthcare provider to present multiple examples of potentially
68 challenging scenarios and ask patients to rate the level of difficulty of hearing in such situations.
69 However, it is possible for patients to either overestimate or underestimate their actual level of
70 difficulty. This can be caused due to several factors;

71 A) Memory bias: Patients may forget details of their experiences over time (Bradburn et
72 al., 1987). B) Context sensitivity: The environment in which the questionnaire is completed, as
73 well as the respondent's current mood, can influence how listening experiences are rated. For
74 example, if the interview is conducted in a quiet room, the ratings regarding proposed noisy
75 environments may be affected (Reis, 2018). C) Recency effect: Events that are closer in time to
76 the day the questionnaire is administered may be weighted more than those that happened further
77 in the past (Kahneman et al., 1999). D) Belief-consistent bias: Responses may reflect an
78 individual's general beliefs about their hearing, rather than the ability to listen in a specific given
79 listening situation (Robinson and Clore, 2002). E) Deviation from real-world diversity: Despite
80 including a variety of potentially complex situations, it is not possible to propose a complete range
81 of situations in which individuals experience hearing difficulties in daily life.

82 Several standardized self-report questionnaires have been developed to assess perceived
83 hearing difficulties and hearing aid outcomes, each emphasizing different aspects of hearing-
84 related experiences and outcomes. These include, among others, the Speech, Spatial and Qualities
85 of Hearing Scale (SSQ; Gatehouse & Noble, 2004), which assesses perceived hearing abilities
86 across speech understanding, spatial hearing, and sound quality dimensions; the Hearing Handicap

87 Inventory (HHI; Newman et al., 1990), which focuses on the social and emotional consequences
88 of hearing loss; International Outcome Inventory for Hearing Aids (IOI-HA; Cox & Alexander,
89 2002), which provides a brief standardized measure of hearing aid outcomes, including use, benefit,
90 satisfaction, and impact on daily life; and the Client-Oriented Scale of Improvement questionnaire
91 (COSI; Dillon et al., 1997), which is a patient-centered instrument that allows individuals to define
92 personally relevant listening situations and assess perceived benefit following intervention.

93 In the **second** approach, assessments are conducted directly within real-life listening
94 situations, where information is captured in the moment, on spot through sensors and/or
95 questionnaires. Therefore, patients' hearing is evaluated while they are naturally exposed to
96 environmental and social factors. This real-time, context-oriented data collection strategy is known
97 as Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA), which allows for the systematic collection of data
98 in everyday situations while reducing memory bias (Shiffman et al., 2008; Stone et al., 2007).
99 Within audiological research, EMA has been mostly used in the monitoring and assessment of
100 tinnitus and hearing aids usage and benefit (Holube et al., 2020; Schinkel-Bielefeld et al., 2024).
101 It is important to note that perceived hearing difficulties and hearing-aid satisfaction are influenced
102 by multiple interacting factors beyond the listening environment itself. These include device-
103 related characteristics (e.g., sound quality and wearing comfort), as well as user-related factors
104 (e.g., attention, motivation, and cognitive resources). For example, directing attention toward
105 positive listening experiences can enhance perceived hearing-aid benefit, independent of acoustic
106 conditions (Lelic et al., 2024). While EMA can reduce recall bias compared to retrospective self-
107 report measures by capturing experiences closer to their events, it cannot compensate for all factors
108 contributing to hearing-aid outcomes.

109 In the **third** approach, simulating real-life scenarios, auditory and visual cues that naturally
110 occur in daily life situations are recreated virtually in laboratory settings. Recent studies have been
111 performed using audio-visual simulated scenes in multiple common and challenging daily-life
112 scenarios (Mansour et al., 2021; van de Par et al., 2022; Afghah et al., 2025; Gerken et al., 2026).
113 This method is highly advantageous as it reduces costs and implementation barriers, allowing all
114 required measurements to be performed in a healthcare facility, as opposed to multiple real
115 environments. Furthermore, as the simulated scenes are similar for all patients, it is possible to
116 define criteria and additional standards for classifying degrees of hearing loss, based on patients'
117 performance in these unified scenes.

118 However, despite extensive effort to realistically simulate these scenes, it is not possible to
119 fully recreate real-life listening experiences in a laboratory. Behavioral, social, and emotional
120 factors involved in real-life conversation and communication tasks are not replicated in such
121 simulations. This includes both the aspects which further challenge the communication task, such
122 as the anxiety of communicating with an unfamiliar person in public places, or reducing task
123 complexity, such as applying nonverbal communication techniques like eye contact and body
124 language. Additionally, similar to the first approach, it is not possible to simulate all situations that
125 naturally occur in daily life, as these environments include only selected examples of everyday
126 situations and therefore cannot capture the full range of real-life experiences. Most importantly, in
127 this approach, it is not possible to individualize or personalize the simulated environments to match
128 individuals' unique real-world communication contexts, which include daily listening demands,
129 acoustic environments, social interaction patterns, communication partners, lifestyle, and habits.

130 This study introduces a novel methodological approach that integrates the advantages of
131 the first and second approaches, i.e., self-report questionnaires and real-time data collection. For

132 this purpose, among commonly used clinical questionnaires, COSI was selected because, in
133 contrast to other surveys, it is patient-centered, which allows for fully individualized identification
134 of relevant listening situations, and is highly sensitive to meaningful functional changes, which
135 makes it suitable for integration within a real-time assessment approach.

136 Traditionally, COSI is administered in clinical interviews to identify personalized hearing
137 goals and evaluate post-intervention outcomes and benefits. Unlike fixed-item questionnaires,
138 patients are instructed to consider up to five listening situations that they find most important in
139 everyday life. These situations are described in patients' own words to form a tailored set of
140 rehabilitation goals. Following the intervention, such as hearing aid fitting, the degree of change
141 and the final ability to hear in those specific situations are rated using standardized ordinal rating
142 scales., as a personalized measure of benefit assessment. As it directly reflects the patient's own
143 listening needs and expectations, COSI is widely valued for its utility in counseling and
144 documenting outcomes that align with everyday communication demands. The original COSI
145 questionnaire is included in the supplementary material. However, as the situations are self-defined
146 by each patient, there is no standardized framework for unifying the intervention outcome across
147 patients. In addition, differences in the examiner's verbal instructions or interview approach may
148 affect how situations are described and rated.

149 The COSI-EMA integration is achieved by utilizing two questionnaires adapted from COSI
150 within an EMA framework, rather than being administered solely through traditional interview-
151 based procedures. This approach benefits from the patient-centered focus of COSI and enhanced
152 ecological validity characteristics of EMA, which together results in providing a practical tool for
153 both research and clinical applications. Specifically, the COSI questionnaire served as the
154 foundation for developing two distinct app-based EMA questionnaires for the pre- and post-

155 intervention phases. Unlike the traditional administration of COSI, where patients nominate
156 situations in their own words through an interview-driven goal-setting process, a systematic
157 framework was designed to provide a wide range of potential candidate listening situations to
158 support structured, real-time reporting with on-the-spot ratings. Potentially challenging listening
159 situations were categorized based on four factors: Primary location of the listening situation (at
160 home, on the way, in social settings, or at work), secondary location or activity (e.g., kitchen, office,
161 watching TV), the sound to which the listener attends (target sound), and the other sounds in the
162 environment (masker sounds).

163 The applicability and efficiency of this approach were evaluated in three directions: first,
164 by evaluating the implementation challenges, second by identifying the most commonly reported
165 real-world listening challenges across individuals, and third, by evaluating the extent to which it
166 can effectively assess the hearing aids benefits for first-time users in their daily environments.
167 Based on these objectives, the current study addressed three research questions:

168 **1. Feasibility and practical implementation considerations;**

169 Using the COSI-EMA integration approach, what practical challenges arise by applying
170 the available hardware and software?

171 **2. Phase one: Approach applicability at the group level: identification of real-world**
172 **listening challenges and group-level differences:**

173 Using the COSI-EMA integration approach, what are the most commonly reported real-
174 world listening challenges among individuals with normal hearing, hearing aid users, and non-
175 users with hearing impairment, across a variety of daily life scenarios?

176 **3.Phase two: Approach applicability in assessing hearing-aid benefit;**

177 Using the COSI-EMA integration approach, and focusing on the most challenging listening
178 experiences identified in phase one, were hearing aids beneficial for first-time users?

179 **2. Method**

180 Data collection was carried out using a hardware package including a smartphone and wearable
181 microphones. An Android application (olMEGA app), developed specifically for performing EMA
182 studies, was used to administer questionnaires and collect environmental data.

183 **2.1 olMEGA system**

184 The olMEGA system is an EMA platform that uses two microphones attached to eyeglasses
185 together with a compact wireless binaural (two-channel) Bluetooth audio transmitter. This setup
186 enables experiments to be supplemented with objective acoustic data while maintaining
187 participants' privacy (Kowalk et al., 2020). In addition, the system includes a questionnaire tool.
188 Questionnaires are created using a simple text-based format that supports designs ranging from
189 basic linear sequences to more advanced interactive structures. The olMEGA system operates on
190 smartphones or tablet devices. The olMEGA Android app was further advanced in this study by
191 applying the findings of extensive User Experience (UX) research. Within two rounds of pilot
192 studies with an overall total of 15 participants, including both normal hearing and hearing impaired,
193 multiple modifications were applied. In this study, the primary advancements to the app were
194 implemented to ensure a stable and continuous connection between the microphones' transmitter
195 and the smartphone. Furthermore, multiple features were added to the app according to the
196 suggestions provided by the pilot participants, as well as those that experimenters found essential
197 to be embedded. The app automatically launches after the phone is turned on and allows for

198 activating "Android Kiosk Mode" internally. By activating this feature, the phone was controlled
199 by the olMEGA app and can only be used for the purpose of study.

200 **2.2 Hardware**

201 Motorola Moto G9 smartphones were used for data collection. Their 6.5-inches screens provided
202 a larger text preview and allowed for a sparser display of the questions and response options,
203 compared with the height of a typical smartphone screen. This feature was especially advantageous
204 for older participants with reduced vision. The microphones, collecting objective data, were
205 mounted on the temples of eyeglasses frames, in order to position them near the participant's ears.
206 However, these data were not analyzed in the present study. For three participants who did not
207 normally wear glasses, a pair of non-corrective glasses was provided.

208 **2.3 Participants**

209 Participants were recruited from the participant database of volunteers for research studies
210 maintained at Hörzentrum Oldenburg gGmbH. The pure-tone audiometry of these volunteers had
211 been recorded in the database, and the recruitment was performed based on this available data,
212 considering the age range of 18 to 85. For six participants, audiometry was performed on the same
213 day as their first appointment. For the remaining participants, audiometric data had been recorded
214 within the previous six months; therefore, repeating the measurements was not required.
215 Acousticians verified that the selected elderly participants had the ability to operate smartphones
216 and use email independently.

217 Given that the current study was a preliminary assessment of a novel experimental design,
218 a small sample size was selected to evaluate the feasibility of the study protocol and to identify
219 potential implementation barriers. Initially 24 participants were recruited and started the

220 experiment, among which two participants withdrew due to illness, one withdrew due to
221 experiencing severe tinnitus after hearing aid fitting, and one withdrew due to hardware usage
222 inconvenience (a total dropout rate of 16.7%). Therefore, twenty participants completed the
223 experiment, categorized into three groups:

- 224 1. **NH group** (n = 4): Normal-hearing individuals with a PTA of less than 20 dB HL.
- 225 2. **HI-ownHA group** (n = 7): Hearing-impaired participants (mild to moderate HL) who
226 used their own hearing aids in daily life.
- 227 3. **HI-noHA group** (n = 9): Hearing-impaired participants (mild to moderate HL) who
228 did not use hearing aids prior to the study.

229 Demographic information, including age, gender distribution, and pure-tone average of the
230 better and worse ears (averaged across 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) for each participant, is provided in
231 Supplementary material, Table 1. Across all participants, the mean age was 69.0 years (SD = 13.3
232 years), with 55% female. For hearing-impaired participants, the average PTA of the better and
233 worse ear were 31.5 dB HL (SD = 9.9 dB) and 35.4 dB HL (SD = 12.2 dB), respectively.

234 The ethics of the study were approved by the Commission for Research Impact Assessment
235 and Ethics of the University of Oldenburg (Drs.EK/2021/031-02). Participants were asked to sign
236 the consent forms and compensated 14 EURO per hour for participation at the facility, and 40
237 EURO per week for app usage. A user manual in German (participants' native language) was
238 provided to familiarize the participant with the aim of the study and the hardware/software
239 components. Furthermore, the acousticians provided participants with training on how to use the
240 app and complete the questionnaires. As part of this training, each participant completed a sample
241 questionnaire on the smartphone under the supervision of the acoustician to ensure familiarity with
242 the procedure, which was later excluded from outcome analyses. Furthermore, participants were

243 explicitly instructed to avoid using the app in situations where doing so could cause a safety risk,
244 most importantly while driving. The contact information of the responsible acoustician was
245 included in the user manual, and participants were instructed to reach out with any questions or
246 technical issues that might arise during the study.

247 **2.4 Experimental Procedure**

248 **2.4.1 Study Timeline**

249 The data collection was performed between March and Jun 2025. The study was conducted using
250 two distinct procedures, which varied based on the participants' hearing status and hearing aid use.
251 Figure 1 illustrates the experimental timeline, divided into two phases. Phase one involved all
252 participants collecting data over one week. Phase two included only the HI-noHA group, who
253 collected data for the second time in aided conditions, following hearing aid fitting, 5-6 weeks of
254 daily life hearing aid use, and fine-tuning (where needed).

255 **Insert Figure 1 here.**

256

257 **2.4.2 Phase One (All participants)**

258 **Questionnaire one:** This questionnaire was used for all participant groups during phase one in
259 German. The English version of it is demonstrated in Table 1. The German version is provided in
260 Supplementary Material, Table 2. The content validity of the modified questionnaire was assessed
261 by linking the questions to the World Health Organization's International Classification of
262 Functioning Disability and Health (ICF) framework (WHO 2001, 2013), brief Core Set for Hearing
263 Loss (Danermark et al., 2010, 2013; Granberg 2015), as recommended in Afghah & Wagener
264 2025b and Afghah et al., 2023. The results can be found in the Supplementary Material, Table 3.

265

Insert Table 1 here.

266

Usage instructions for questionnaire completion: After receiving the hardware package

267

during phase one, visit one, each participant was instructed, both verbally and through the written

268

manual, to fill in a questionnaire whenever they experienced a change in their acoustic

269

environment, in order to capture a wide variety of listening situations throughout daily life. Several

270

examples were provided to clarify what changes in the acoustic environment meant. Such changes

271

included moving to a new primary location among the four (i.e. at home, on the way, in social

272

settings, or at work), moving to another secondary location / performing a new activity within the

273

same primary location (e.g., from being in kitchen to watching TV), shifting the listening intention

274

from one sound to another (i.e., the listening target sound), or experiencing changes in additional

275

sounds, apart from the main intended sound (i.e., the masker sounds).

276

As the focus of the study was specifically on experiences involving hearing impairment,

277

the progression of each questionnaire depended on the participant's perceived challenge in the new

278

event. If the participants did not feel impaired in the situation, the event was not considered

279

relevant to the study. This filtering of non-challenging listening situations was implemented

280

through Q2: when participants selected "not at all impaired" or "very little impaired," the

281

questionnaire was automatically terminated.

282

As participants might unintentionally overlook some challenging situations during

283

everyday activities, the application included an automatic reminder to reduce the likelihood of

284

missed events. If no questionnaire had been completed within 3 h of the previous submission, the

285

app generated a 10 s vibration and meanwhile showed a red blinking reminder note on screen. In

286

this case, participants were advised to complete a questionnaire following this prompt, in case a

287

change in the acoustic environment had occurred since their last completed questionnaire. The

288 vibration duration can be adjusted based on the experimenter's preferences. Based on feedback
289 provided by pilot participants, if the phone vibrates while the user was driving or engaged in an
290 activity that needs to be performed cautiously, a long vibration duration could be distracting and
291 potentially endangering the user. Therefore, in this study, it was set to a relatively short period for
292 safety reasons. In both phases, participants were instructed to complete questionnaires also on the
293 days of their visits (i.e., when they received or returned the hardware package).

294 **2.4.3 Phase Two (HI-noHA group)**

295 In this phase, participants in HI-noHA group received hearing aids. All participants received
296 bilateral upper mid-range hearing aids with domes, using either Signia Pure Charge&Go 5Nx or
297 Phonak Audeo M70-R. They were fitted by an experienced acoustician, based on the individuals'
298 sound level preference, and daily needs and routines and applying the first fit procedure of the
299 manufacturer's own fitting software, based on individual pure tone audiogram data and open loop
300 gain feedback measurements. Individual fine tuning was applied. After a week of wearing hearing
301 aids in everyday life, fine tuning followed. If necessary, further weekly fine-tuning appointments
302 were provided.

303 Adjustments were made based on participant feedback. No real-ear measurements (REM-
304 based) verification procedures were conducted, as the primary objective of this study was to
305 evaluate the feasibility of capturing self-reported listening experiences and perceived benefit
306 within a real-world EMA framework, rather than to optimize electroacoustic fitting parameters
307 under controlled laboratory conditions. Participants were not offered the option to purchase or
308 retain the hearing aids after completion of the study. Laboratory-based objective outcome
309 measures, such as aided speech audiometry, were not performed, as the central focus of the study
310 was on self-reported outcomes. In addition to the COSI-EMA assessments, all participants

311 completed the HEAR-COMMAND Tool, which is a comprehensive self-report questionnaire
312 assessing hearing, functioning, communication, and conversational abilities (Afghah et al., 2022;
313 2024; Alfakir et al., 2025a; 2025b). While COSI-EMA captures situation-specific, momentary
314 experiences, the HEAR-COMMAND Tool offers a broader perspective on overall hearing-related
315 functioning. A detailed analysis of HEAR-COMMAND Tool outcomes is beyond the scope of the
316 present methodological paper; therefore, only a general overview of the HI-noHA group's
317 responses before and after hearing aid fitting is provided in the Supplementary material, section
318 HEAR-COMMAND Tool.

319 For each participant of the HI-noHA group, based on the data collected in phase one, up to
320 five of the most challenging listening situations were identified to be further evaluated during
321 phase two, referred to as assigned EMA-based listening environments. Unlike in phase one, where
322 data could be collected in any naturally occurring daily-life situation, in phase two, each participant
323 was instructed to fill in questionnaires exclusively within these assigned EMA-based listening
324 environments. The following four steps were taken to identify them.

325 **Step 1, Identifying occurred auditory scenes:** The response options were summarized
326 to a total of 7 target and 8 masker sound groups, as shown in Table 2. As a result, a total of 56
327 possible combinations of target-masker could occur, hereafter referred to as auditory scenes.
328 Questionnaires in which participants, in response to the presence of a target sound, selected either
329 'No one and nothing' or 'It is quiet', were excluded from further analysis. As each questionnaire
330 allowed only one target sound, but one or more masker sounds, a single questionnaire could be
331 described by multiple target-masker combinations.

332 **Step 2, Selecting questionnaires of interest:** To select the questionnaires whose responses
333 were used to define assigned EMA-based listening environments, three key questions were
334 selected to jointly capture complementary dimensions of real-world listening challenge:
335 "Importance of hearing in the situation" (Q3), "Concentration difficulty" (Q18), and "Self-
336 perceived hearing impairment degree" (Q2). Based on the objectives of this study, as the three
337 factors were not expected to contribute equally to perceived challenge, a weighting scheme using
338 weighting coefficients was applied to their responses to reflect their relative contribution.

339 “Importance of hearing in the situation” (Q3): The highest weighting coefficient was
340 assigned to this factor , as it directly distinguishes active from passive listening. Listening
341 situations rated as highly important are typically more engaging and therefore place greater
342 demands on sustained attention and cognitive effort to separate target sounds from competing
343 background noise. Prioritizing listening situations with high perceived importance therefore
344 ensures that the EMA-based selection emphasizes contexts that are most meaningful to participants
345 and most informative for guiding subsequent hearing-aid adjustments.

346 “Concentration difficulty” (Q18): This relates to the participant's perceived ability to
347 perform the auditory task. Higher difficulty concentrating can result in poor ability to focus on the
348 perceived sound and as a result decrease the capacity to segregate auditory streams, making a
349 listening task more complex and challenging. Within the EMA framework, concentration difficulty
350 therefore serves as a listening situation-specific, patient-centered measure of perceived listening
351 effort, which provides an index with high ecological validity of cognitive load associated with
352 real-world hearing challenges.

353 “Self-perceived hearing impairment degree” (Q2): This factor was assigned the lowest
354 weighting coefficient, because, although it indicates a general level of difficulty, it does not
355 directly reflect specific cognitive demands required to manage a given complex listening situation,
356 as it may also be influenced by more general self-assessments rather than moment-to-moment
357 evaluations.

358 Each response option for these three questions was assigned a numerical value on a 1 to 7
359 Likert scale, with higher values indicating a greater degree of perceived challenge. Therefore, the
360 following responses were assigned to number 7: extremely impaired (Q2), very important (Q3),
361 and extremely difficult (Q18). For each questionnaire, at first, the raw scores for questions Q2, Q3,
362 and Q18 were normalized to a 0 to 1 scale by dividing by the maximum possible score (7). Then,
363 each normalized score was multiplied by its respective assigned weighting coefficient: 0.40 for
364 Q3, 0.35 for Q18, and 0.25 for Q2. These coefficients were determined according to the specific
365 information needed in phase one to design phase two. Therefore, they are ultimately arbitrary,
366 study-specific assumptions rather than universal values. The resulting weighted values were
367 summed to produce a single "weighted score" for the given questionnaire. All questionnaires were
368 then sorted in descending order based on their weighted scores. Questionnaires within the top 50%
369 of weighted scores, representing the self-reported most challenging listening situations, were
370 selected for further analysis.

371 **Step 3, Reproducing auditory scenes:** As the primary objective of the analysis was to
372 identify which target sounds were most challenging to segregate from competing maskers, the
373 subsequent analysis focused on the frequency of occurrence of target sound groups within the top
374 50% of questionnaires ranked by perceived challenge. The scene reproduction process started with

375 the most repeated target group, which was then paired with up to three of the most frequently co-
376 occurring masker groups and locations. Therefore, a maximum of three target-masker pairs could
377 be recreated for each target group. This algorithm was terminated after reproducing a maximum
378 of 14 scenes.

379 **Step 4: Selecting auditory scenes:** The proposed algorithm served as a decision-support
380 tool to identify and prioritize relevant scenes and to ensure reproducible translation of EMA
381 feedback into candidate auditory scenes. Standardized scene prioritization was achieved through
382 a consistent sorting process and application of the same algorithm across all participants. Final
383 authority over scene selection for each participant remained with the acoustician to ensure
384 participant comfort and practical feasibility, as in some cases, it may be impractical to expect
385 participants to complete questionnaires exclusively for the exact same scene in everyday life.

386 For maximum practicality, the acousticians implemented two approaches: 1) The
387 acousticians grouped up to three acoustically similar reproduced scenes into one out of five pre-
388 defined phase two assigned EMA-based listening environments for each participant, taking into
389 account that the scenes had been reproduced in order of priority. In some cases where multiple
390 scenes were reproduced with the same target but different maskers, the listening environment was
391 defined by specifying the target and location, along with the explanation "in the presence of other
392 sounds." Example: Target group 3: Speech over communication devices, masker a: Direct speech,
393 more than one person, masker b: Live speech, Loudspeaker, masker c: Live non-speech,
394 dishes/appliance. 2) The acousticians presented the defined EMA-based listening environments to
395 the participants and asked for their verbal feedback on how feasible it would be to revisit these
396 environments, based on their individual lifestyle and habits.

397 To provide the acoustician with sufficient details to determine which scenes should
398 ultimately be selected as up to five assigned EMA-based listening environments in phase two, the
399 following characteristics were presented for each scene; The most repeated target group and its
400 repetition across the top 50% of questionnaires over all primary and secondary locations, the paired
401 masker group, the most common corresponding locations, and the average weighted score of the
402 questionnaires containing the target group.

403 **Questionnaire Two:** The second questionnaire was developed for participants in the HI-
404 noHA group during phase two. It started with the same first three questions as the questionnaire
405 one. However, unlike questionnaire one, this questionnaire did not terminate if the response to Q2
406 (Self-perceived hearing impairment degree) was "not at all impaired" or "very little impaired".
407 This change was made as a lower level of perceived impairment could potentially indicate that the
408 hearing aids were effective in the given listening environment.

409 Question 4 presented the reproduced EMA-based listening environments selected by the
410 acoustician with detailed explanation of target, maskers, primary and secondary locations. When
411 required for a participant, additional details could be provided by the acoustician and accessed on
412 a follow-up screen by clicking on the "more info" option. Sample response options for this question,
413 representing three EMA-based listening environments, are provided here (translated into English).

414 *Situation 1: At home / outside in garden or balcony / while conversing with one person /*
415 *with natural sounds in the background.*

416 *Situation 2: On the way / walking outside / while calling on a cellphone / in the presence*
417 *of other sounds such as engine sounds.*

418 *Situation 3: In social settings / in a restaurant, coffeeshop, shop / while communicating*
419 *with one or more people, in the presence of other sounds such as other people, dishes, devices.*

420 The remaining self-report measures questions (Q17-Q26) were presented in the same order
421 as phase one questionnaire. At the end, an additional question was included in this questionnaire
422 to evaluate hearing aid benefit and satisfaction: "How helpful are your hearing aids in this
423 situation? (compared to how it would be without hearing aids)".

424 **2.4.4 Data analysis and statistics**

425 To compare performance across phases, for each participant, all questionnaires completed in phase
426 two were considered and the target sound of these questionnaires were extracted. Then, among the
427 completed questionnaires in phase one, only those with targets similar to these extracted target
428 sounds were considered. This approach was applied to ensure that the auditory scenes compared
429 across phases are as similar as possible. This filtering is practically meaningful because, as
430 mentioned in step 4, acousticians merged some of the reproduced scenes with shared targets and
431 provided them as a single listening environment in which the phase two questionnaires were to be
432 filled in.

433 Due to differences in the data type of response options, different mathematical analyses
434 were applied to present the outcomes, as described below.

435 For phase one, nominal data corresponding to the selected primary and secondary locations,
436 target sounds, and masker sounds are summarized by reporting the absolute number of instances
437 for each response option. For group-level comparisons, raw frequency counts are presented, and
438 for the overall results across all participants, percentages of the total counts are provided.
439 Responses to Q23, Q25, and Q26 are presented using the percentage of total counts.

440 As in both phases, the number of completed questionnaires varied across participants, a
441 normalization procedure was applied to responses to Q2, Q3, Q17-Q22, and Q24. This was to
442 ensure that each participant contributed equally and to reduce bias from individuals who completed
443 a larger number of questionnaires. To do so, an across-participant mean is presented. To calculate
444 this mean, for each participant, the relative proportion of responses within each category was
445 calculated, resulting in one value per category per participant. These proportions for a given
446 category were then averaged across participants to provide relative percentages.

447 As an illustrative example for listening effort (Q17) over three participants, assume
448 Participant A completed 10 applicable questionnaires and selected “Very effortful” 4 times (40%),
449 Participant B completed 4 questionnaires and selected “Very effortful” 2 times (50%), and
450 Participant C completed 6 questionnaires and selected “Very effortful” 2 times (33.3%). The
451 across-participant mean for the category “Very effortful” is calculated as the average of 40%, 50%,
452 and 33.3%, resulting in 41.1%. To visualize these percentages, stacked bar charts were used, in
453 which for each bar, each colored segment corresponds to the across-participant mean within a
454 specific category.

455 To compare the responses to Q2, Q3, Q17-Q22, and Q24 across phases, a cumulative link
456 mixed model (CLMM) was applied, considering a random intercept for participants, with phase (1
457 = unaided, 2 = aided) as the fixed effect. Results are reported as unaided-vs-aided logit coefficients
458 (β), p-value, and 95% confidence intervals. As set up, $\beta > 0$ indicates that the unaided condition
459 (phase one) has higher odds of choosing higher response categories than the aided condition (phase
460 two). For instance, for Q2 (Self-perceived hearing impairment degree), a positive β represents a
461 higher likelihood of reporting larger value on scale of 1:7 (7: Extremely impaired) in phase one
462 which reflects hearing aid was beneficial in this case.

463 To analyze the weighted scores, continuous variables in the range of 0 to 1, a linear mixed-
464 effects model (LMM) was applied, considering a random intercept for participants. Data analysis
465 was performed using MATLAB 2021b, IBM SPSS statistics v.25, and R 4.5.1.

466 **3 Results**

467 **3.1 Feasibility and practical implementation considerations**

468 **3.1.1 Interpersonal and data privacy considerations**

469 Some pilot participants reported that they found carrying and using the hardware package to be
470 "embarrassing", particularly in social gatherings. Furthermore, their conversation partners
471 expressed concern regarding their voices being recorded, despite being reassured by the participant
472 that no raw audio was being stored. Based on this feedback, during the recruitment procedure of
473 the current study, acousticians explained the physical features of the package to potential
474 participants to ensure they are aware of the physical demands of using the package. After the
475 explanations were provided, due to data safety concerns, some volunteers refused to participate,
476 particularly those who had frequent interpersonal interactions with unfamiliar individuals in the
477 workplace. For example, a healthcare provider who was contacted refused to participate due to
478 concerns about maintaining patient confidentiality while wearing microphones and a cashier
479 refused due to possible negative reactions from the shop customers.

480 **3.1.2 Wearability considerations in daily use**

481 Participants reported that the microphones' wires and non-corrective glasses made the usage of the
482 hardware package inconvenient. Particularly, hearing aid users found wearing both the hearing
483 aids and the mounted microphone simultaneously problematic, as it increased the risk of the

484 hearing aid falling off and being lost. Participants who wore different glasses during the day
485 claimed that they were not able to fill in the questionnaires during times when another pair of
486 glasses was used.

487 **3.1.3. Temporal commitment considerations**

488 Additionally, some participants reported that they cannot be committed to performing a task on a
489 daily basis. Based on the objectives of phase one, one possibility would be extending the EMA
490 data collection duration to 10-14 days to potentially increase the likelihood of capturing a broader
491 range of listening contexts and allow for skipping some days (Break days) to reduce participant
492 burden.

493 **3.1.4. Bluetooth connectivity and stability considerations**

494 Maintaining a stable Bluetooth connection between the smartphone and microphone transmitter
495 over a period of one week was challenging, as several participants reported temporary
496 disconnections during data collection. In the event of a connection drop, automated reconnection
497 procedures were implemented to restore communication between the app and the transmitter. If
498 automated re-connection failed, the participants were instructed to manually turn the transmitter
499 off and on again with its built-in switch to re-establish the connection.

500 **3.2 Approach applicability at the group level: demonstration of differences**

501 **(Phase One)**

502 In this section, data collected from all participants in phase one is presented, reported either as raw
503 frequency counts or as relative percentages, shown either overall across all participants or, where
504 relevant, separated by group.

526 as “other”. This value was 20% for both “on the way” and “in social settings”. No participant in
527 the HI-ownHA group ever reported listening to music.

528 **Target sounds:** Figure 3, the middle panel compares the distribution of target sounds
529 across groups. Across all participants, nearly half of the reported target sounds represented
530 conversation-based listening challenges, including 27% listening to a single person and 25%
531 listening to more than one person. Across all participants, the second most frequently reported
532 category of target sounds was "media devices". This included 13% related to listening to speech
533 from TV/Radio and 16% related to other media content such as non-speech TV/Radio or music, a
534 combined total of 29%.

535 **Masker sounds:** Figure 3, the bottom panel compares the distribution of masker sounds
536 across groups. Across all participants, a total of 30% of the masker sounds were "one or more
537 people." In the HI-ownHA group, the most reported masker sound was "devices/dishes/engine
538 noise".

539 **Auditory scenes:** Table 2 illustrates all possible predefined auditory scenes in phase one,
540 represented as two-by-two combinations of target and masker sounds. As noted, a single completed
541 questionnaire may correspond to more than one scene when the target is accompanied by multiple
542 maskers. Target sounds are displayed in rows and masker sounds in columns. Numbers in each
543 cell indicate the number of times the corresponding scene was reported across all participants of
544 the given group, using the notation "×Nr.". The cells are color-coded as follows; NH (Top, orange),
545 HI-ownHA (Middle, green), and HI-noHA (Bottom, blue). A white blank cell indicates that the
546 corresponding scene was not reported by any participants in the given group. In all three groups,
547 the most frequently reported auditory scene was when "more than one person" as the target and
548 "more than one person" as the masker sounds were present.

549

550 **Self-report measures questions:** Figure 4 illustrates the group-level responses to these
551 questions in phase one.

552

Insert Figure 4 here.

553

554

555

556

557

558

559

560

561

562

563

564

Across NH group, 66% of responses to listening effort (Q17) were in the lowest effort categories (“Effortless” or “Very little effortful”), compared with only 17% for HI-ownHA and 4% for HI-noHA groups. Regarding concentration difficulty (Q18), across NH group, 22% of responses were reported “Not at all difficult,” while less than 1% of responses of HI-noHA group were selected as this category. Across NH group, 39% of responses to speech comprehension (Q19) were rated as “Perfect” or “Very good.” In contrast, no participant in HI-ownHA and HI-noHA selected “Perfect”. Across NH group, 50% of the responses to sound localization (Q22) were "Very good" or "Perfect" while 21% of HI-ownHa and 16% of HI-noHA responses were either of these two categories. In response to immersion in conversation (Q24), 56% of NH were chosen as "Fully immersed", while this was the case for 24% and 19% of responses for HI-ownHA and HI-noHA, respectively. Overall, the NH group consistently reported ratings corresponding to better listening outcomes across the selected measures.

565

3.3 Approach applicability in hearing-aid benefit illustration (Phase Two)

566

567

Responses to the selected self-report measures questions from phases one and two are visualized in Figure 5 and the outcomes of the CLMM analysis of these responses are provided in Table 3.

568

Insert Figure 5 here.

569

Insert Table 3 here.

570 The phase effect in this analysis reflects the impact of hearing aid fitting, as the condition
571 shifts from unaided listening in phase one to aided listening in phase two. Significant phase-related
572 improvements were observed for most self-report domains, with positive logit coefficients and p-
573 values < 0.001. The largest effect was found for speech comprehension (Q19), followed by hearing
574 impairment (Q2), concentration difficulty (Q18), listening effort (Q17), sound localization (Q22),
575 pleasantness of sound (Q21), and immersion in conversation (Q24).

576 Loudness perception (Q20) with 7 assigned to "too quiet" showed a negative logit
577 coefficient, indicating the perceived loudness increased in phase two. The perceived importance
578 of the listening situation (Q3) did not change significantly across phases ($\beta = -0.39$, $p = 0.196$).
579 This indicates that the phase condition had no measurable effect on participants' ratings of
580 importance. This is because, during the recreation of acoustic scenes, those with the 50% highest
581 weighted scores were selected, with importance receiving the highest weighting coefficient. In line
582 with the principle applied for comparison across phases, the perceived importance of the listening
583 situations was maintained at similar levels. Therefore, the absence of a phase effect reflects this
584 selection principle. In other words, it represents a methodological constraint inherent to the study
585 design rather than a diminished role of importance in shaping listening experiences. Consequently,
586 the limited variability in importance ratings across phases was an expected outcome of the study
587 design and should not be interpreted as evidence that importance was less influential than other
588 questionnaire dimensions.

589 In CLMM analysis, to focus on hearing aid benefits in participants' auditory functioning
590 outcomes, some questions were excluded and are reviewed in the following using percentage of
591 occurrence. Question 23 (familiarity of sounds): The response option "Familiar" was increased
592 from 43% in phase one to 59% in phase two. Question 25 (perceived conversation difficulty for

593 the partner): The options "Not at all" and "Very little difficult" combined increased by 15%. The
594 responses in the range of "Fairly" to "Extremely difficult" were not selected in phase two. Question
595 26 (current mood): The option "Very happy" was increased by 18% and the options "Sad" and
596 "Very sad" were not chosen. Question 27 (hearing aid satisfaction): Overall, in 58% of the
597 questionnaires, participants reported that their hearing aid was either 'Very' or 'Extremely'
598 beneficial. The options "Little", "Very Little", and "Not at all" were chosen in 10% of the
599 questionnaires.

600 The LMM analysis of weighted scores showed a significant effect of phase (hearing aid
601 fitting), with a negative logit coefficient reflecting lower weighted scores in the aided condition
602 compared to the unaided condition ($\beta = -0.76$, $SE = 0.06$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-0.89, -0.64]). The
603 estimated means were 0.64 for phase one and 0.45 for phase two.

604 **4 Discussion**

605 This study introduced a new methodology that utilized the COSI questionnaire in everyday life by
606 embedding it within an EMA data collection procedure. This was implemented through a two-
607 phase experimental design. In phase one, the COSI-EMA integration approach was applied to
608 capture self-reported listening challenges as they occurred across diverse everyday environments
609 among participants with different hearing status. By applying this approach, it was possible to
610 systematically identify and differentiate listening difficulties across participant groups, based on
611 hearing status. In phase two, the COSI-EMA integration approach was used to evaluate the extent
612 to which first-time hearing aid users benefited from hearing aid fittings after 5-6 weeks of use.

613 **4.1 Implications of feasibility and study limitations**

614 Overall, the hardware burden and usage difficulty were likely among the factors contributing to
615 the limited number of completed questionnaires. Therefore, despite being instructed and
616 financially compensated to complete the assigned task, participants did not consistently carry the
617 device with them in different environments or may skip filling out a questionnaire when
618 environmental changes occur. This relatively low response rate limits a comprehensive screening
619 of daily life situations and statistically powerful analysis. Although in principle increasing the
620 number of data collection day could potentially allow for collecting more data, some EMA studies
621 have shown extending the duration of data collection does not necessarily yield greater data
622 volume or it can even decline the data rate (Howard & Lamb, 2023; Wrzus & Neubauer, 2022;
623 Tonkin et al., 2023).

624 Considering hearing-impaired participants, 200 out of 427 (47%) completed questionnaires
625 were applicable for further data analysis. In principle, this suggests that they did not feel impaired
626 in such situations taking into account that most of the hearing impairment participants had mild
627 hearing loss. Including participants with moderate to severe hearing loss who do not use hearing
628 aids could potentially increase the number of applicable questionnaires, as they are more likely to
629 feel impaired in a listening situation. However, other explanations are also possible. It may reflect
630 that participants did not experience a broad range of situations or variations in acoustic scenes
631 within the same situation in daily life. Another possibility is that, after completing the
632 questionnaire multiple times, participants may have learned a pattern as to initiate a questionnaire
633 for the sake of completing the task while conveniently terminating it by selecting "Not at all
634 impaired" or "Very little impaired" in response to the second question.

635 Similar technical concerns to those observed in this study were reported by Vercammen et
636 al. (2023), where connectivity issues with hearing aids represented approximately 20% of all
637 participants' reports, followed by reports related to battery life (15%) and physical fit and comfort
638 (5%).

639 A limitation of the present approach is that listening situations identified during phase one
640 could not always be reproduced identically during phase two. However, the aim of the study was
641 not to achieve exact acoustic replication, but rather to preserve a high degree of ecological validity
642 by evaluating functionally comparable listening situations that reflect participants' real-world
643 listening goals. By focusing on target sounds, locations, and typical background sounds, the
644 selected scenes remained representative of the listening challenges identified earlier. This
645 approach supports meaningful interpretation of phase two outcomes while acknowledging the
646 inherent variability of real-world listening conditions.

647 **4.2 Applicability at the group level: demonstration of differences (Phase One)**

648 **Primary and secondary locations/activities:** Almost half of the questionnaires were completed
649 at home. This was expected, as many of the participants were of older age and retired. For such
650 participants, the acoustic situation at home is relatively stable. As a result, their responses cannot
651 be generalized to broader populations with different ages, occupations, and more dynamic daily
652 activities. A more diverse population sample is required to expand the applicability of the study
653 outcomes. An alternative explanation is that both HI-ownHA and HI-noHA groups may have
654 limited their social activities due to their hearing limitations.

655 No participant in the HI-ownHA group reported listening to music, whereas both NH and
656 HI-noHA groups did. Given the small sample size, a concrete conclusion regarding the underlying
657 cause is not possible. Another noticeable observation for this group was that devices/dishes was
658 the most frequently reported masker. This could potentially be related to distortions caused by
659 hearing aids which may increase the perceived annoyance of such sounds.

660 The frequent use of the “others” response option indicates that in order to collect more
661 precise information regarding ongoing activities, more diverse predefined activity options could
662 be added to the currently offered answer choices, beyond what is provided in the COSI
663 questionnaire.

664 **Auditory scenes:** Regarding the combination of target and masker sounds, the most
665 frequently reported challenging auditory scene was conversation with more than one person. This
666 finding was expected, as it is well established that following a multi-talker conversation
667 corresponds to high cognitive engagement and auditory demand, particularly for individuals with
668 hearing impairment. This outcome suggests that the applied questionnaire has strong potential to
669 capture real-life challenging listening situations and can be applied as a reliable tool in clinical
670 applications. This finding is highly encouraging, as it aligns with the current focus on improving
671 hearing aid technologies in enhancing speech intelligibility in communication and conversation
672 contexts.

673 Beyond conversation-based challenges, media listening was the second most common
674 challenging situation reported by participants. This highlights the importance of further improving
675 hearing aid algorithms and connectivity features that facilitate high-quality streaming from media
676 devices. Including a larger number of participants with moderate to severe hearing loss who do

677 not use hearing aids could make media-listening situations more notable in future studies, as these
678 individuals are more likely to experience difficulties and perceive such situations as critical
679 listening challenges.

680 This is in line with the study conducted by Vercammen et al. (2023) who analyzed 8000
681 self-initiated, free-text input ecological momentary assessments from over 2000 hearing-aid users
682 to investigate real-life experiences with hearing devices. The natural language analysis revealed
683 that the most frequently reported context (21% of all responses) concerned "*communication and*
684 *speech intelligibility in challenging listening situations*", particularly those involving multiple
685 speakers in different locations. Furthermore, approximately 12% of the reports related to "*TV*
686 *experience and issues of loudness comfort*."

687 **Self-report measures:** It should be noted that 73% of NH responses to the impairment
688 inquiry (Q2) were selected as "Not applicable," since these participants reported very little to no
689 impairment. As a result, comparisons on other self-report questions were based on the remaining
690 27% of NH responses. While this can potentially create imbalance between groups comparisons,
691 it also demonstrates that the COSI-EMA integration approach accurately reflects the minimal
692 difficulties experienced by NH listeners.

693 At the same time, the COSI-EMA integration approach results revealed clear group
694 differences in reported listening difficulties. The NH group indicated relatively few challenges,
695 whereas both HI-ownHA and HI-noHA participants described more severe problems. The contrast
696 between NH and HI groups was remarkable in listening effort, speech intelligibility, sound
697 localization, perceived impairment, immersion in conversation, and conversation difficulty, which

698 shows that the COSI-EMA integration approach can sensitively capture real-world experiences in
699 complex auditory scenes.

700 **4.3 Applicability in hearing-aid benefit illustration (Phase Two)**

701 Performing data analysis at the level of individual listening environments required a higher volume
702 of questionnaires in similar situations across the two phases for a given environment than was
703 available in most cases, which made per-listening situation comparisons impractical. The
704 questionnaires could, in principle, be compared across phases using the Non-Overlap of All Pairs
705 (NAP) statistics (Parker & Vannest, 2009, 2011; Schinkel-Bielefeld et al., 2024; von Gablenz et
706 al., 2021). However, due to the insufficient number of completed questionnaires for some
707 participants, this method would not yield statistically meaningful results.

708 Nevertheless, combining the responses of all nine fitted participants yielded enough data
709 for applying linear mixed-effects model and cumulative-link mixed model. This analysis showed
710 that the COSI-EMA integration approach is highly capable of revealing consistent and significant
711 benefits of hearing aid fitting in several dimensions. Where this approach was applied in the most
712 challenging listening situations, significant benefit in speech comprehension, self-perceived
713 degree of hearing impairment, concentration difficulty, listening effort, sound localization,
714 pleasantness of sound, and immersion in conversation was observed.

715 In a recent study, Salvago et al. (2024) compared self-reported hearing-aid benefit derived
716 from COSI with audiometric and speech intelligibility measures conducted in unaided laboratory
717 settings. Five predetermined COSI categories were analyzed, including “Television/Radio at
718 normal volume” and “Conversation in quiet and in noise,” in both first-time and experienced

719 hearing aid users. The results showed that pure-tone thresholds and speech intelligibility scores
720 were not reliable predictors of COSI outcomes which were more accurate representation of
721 perceived hearing aid performance. The current study offers advancement by extending the
722 application of the COSI across a wide range of individualized, real-world listening situations and
723 through multiple questionnaires collected over a week. This context-based approach provides
724 richer information with high ecological validity than a single, one-time administration of the COSI
725 conducted in controlled settings.

726 In another recent study, Jorgensen et al. (2025) investigated contributing factors to listening
727 effort and speech intelligibility in hearing aid users using EMA. The analysis, performed on self-
728 reported listening experiences collected in daily-life environments, revealed that among the
729 included environmental factors (i.e., environment type, listening activity, dominant background
730 noise source, sound level, noise location, visual cues, and situation importance), *listening activity*
731 was the strongest predictor of both outcomes, followed by *situation importance*. These
732 relationships were identified post hoc through conditional inference tree analyses of the EMA data.

733 The concept of listening activity in Jorgensen et al. (2025) corresponds to what is referred
734 to as the target sound in the present study. These findings validate the two main assumptions used
735 in the development of the algorithm in the present study: (1) the reproduction of listening scenes
736 for phase two and the comparison of responses across phases one and two were primarily based
737 on the selected target sound, and (2) the ranking of questionnaires from phase one for auditory
738 scene reproduction was performed using a weighted score in which importance received the
739 highest weighting coefficient.

740 **4.4 Considerations for future implementation**

741 The following suggestions are provided to simplify the implementation of the proposed COSI-
742 EMA integration approach and the applications of the proposed questionnaires and the associated
743 algorithm. 1) To overcome barriers caused by the applied wired microphones, in the future, the
744 use of easily removable wireless microphones could be considered.

745 2) To encourage participants to complete questionnaires in public is to install the app
746 directly on their personal smartphone. This approach may be particularly beneficial for elderly
747 people, who might experience greater difficulty managing two phones during social events. In
748 recent years, advancements in wearable technologies, most importantly smartwatches and
749 wristbands, have helped overcome EMA hardware inconvenience and made the implementation
750 more feasible (Bell et al., 2022; El-Toukhy et al., 2023; Kunchay et al., 2024; Rizvi et al., 2024;
751 Fifield et al., 2025).

752 3) Based on the number of completed questionnaires for the majority of participants,
753 providing up to three overall representative EMA-based listening environments found to be more
754 realistic than the initial assumption of up to five environments. As mentioned earlier, although it
755 is theoretically possible to define masker sounds that are repeated in challenging environments,
756 reproducing acoustic scenes with fixed masker configurations can be impractical in everyday
757 implementation. It may be more feasible to focus mainly on specifying target sounds, while also
758 providing examples of the most frequently reported masker sounds.

759 4) To simplify the procedure for older participants, and to increase the likelihood of
760 collecting a larger volume of usable data, a binary decision structure could be implemented in
761 future applications of post-intervention phase. First, using the same algorithm, the most
762 challenging situations could be identified, and acoustically similar ones merged. Then, only two

763 broad priority EMA-based environments would be considered, rather than three to five, and
764 participants would then be instructed to collect data exclusively in either Situation A or Situation
765 B.

766 5) The microphone system could be used to automatically detect changes in the acoustic
767 environment and trigger EMA prompts accordingly. For example, a sudden change in the intensity
768 of the recorded sound beyond a predefined threshold could be used as a trigger in future
769 implementations. While this functionality was not implemented in the present study, which
770 focused on evaluating the feasibility of self-reported EMA questionnaires, microphone-based
771 triggering may provide a more objective and responsive prompting strategy. However, not every
772 detected acoustic change necessarily represents a meaningful listening situation, as a sudden
773 increase in sound level may reflect a loud but irrelevant event. Therefore, when a prompt is
774 activated, the system could first ask participants whether the situation is relevant or important
775 before initiating the full questionnaire. Such an approach could reduce dependence on participant
776 self-initiation and increase the likelihood of capturing relevant changes in listening situations.
777 Future work will be needed to evaluate the feasibility, user acceptance, and privacy implications
778 of integrating automated acoustic triggering into EMA protocols.

779 6) Future studies may reduce insufficient and uneven numbers of completed questionnaires
780 by incorporating partially supervised data collection to achieve a more standardized exposure
781 protocol. For example, in phase two, when participants are instructed to revisit their individually
782 defined challenging listening situations, the examiner could accompany them on several occasions
783 to ensure that a minimum number of questionnaires are completed in these environments. This

784 approach could support a more balanced dataset and enhance the comparability of outcomes across
785 participants.

786 7) A further limitation concerns differences in questionnaire progression between groups resulting
787 from the termination rule applied to Q2 (self-perceived hearing impairment). NH participants
788 frequently selected the lowest impairment categories, which led to early termination of the
789 questionnaire and consequently fewer responses to subsequent questions. Although this reflects
790 the lower perceived listening difficulty in this group, it resulted in fewer detailed responses
791 compared to the HI groups. In future implementations of the COSI-EMA integration approach, a
792 small set of key follow-up questions could be presented regardless of the Q2 response to ensure a
793 comparable set of contextual and outcome measures across groups.

794 **Conclusion**

795 This study proposes a novel methodological framework that integrates the advantages of the
796 Client-Oriented Scale of Improvement (COSI) and Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA).
797 Two questionnaires were developed to implement this approach across two distinct experimental
798 phases. Results from phase one indicated that conversation-based scenarios involving one or more
799 communication partners were most frequently reported as challenging, followed by listening to
800 media devices. The findings show the applicability of the proposed method for identifying and
801 differentiating real-world listening challenges based on hearing status. Outcomes from phase two
802 revealed improvements in primary hearing loss-related dimensions, including speech intelligibility,
803 perceived impairment and difficulty, listening effort, immersion in conversation, pleasantness, and
804 sound localization, in most challenging situations identified during the first phase. The method

805 successfully evaluated the benefits of hearing aid fitting among first-time users in their most
806 challenging everyday listening situations. Furthermore, the study identified primary
807 implementation barriers that may limit the full implementation of the experimental procedures to
808 be considered in future applications of this methodology.

809 Funding

810 This study was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research
811 Foundation) – Project ID: 352015383 – SFB1330, C4 and by the governmental funding initiative
812 zukunft.niedersachsen of the Volkswagen Foundation, project "Data-driven health (DEAL)".

813 ORCID IDS

814 Tahereh Afghah: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-5343-0818>

815 Petra von Gablenz: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7346-7950>

816 Sven Franz: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-0615-0144>

817 Ulrik Kowalk: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2907-7368>

818 Inga Holube: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1936-8855>

819 Kirsten Wagener: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2858-2789>

820 Acknowledgment

821 The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to Janique Reinwaldt, Kevin Rethorn,
822 Holger Groenewold, and Ania Kreuteler for their valuable assistance with data collection and
823 performing hearing aid fittings.

824 Data Availability Statement

825 The data collected during the current study are not publicly available, due to ethical/privacy
826 restrictions: participants did not consent to the public sharing of their individual data.

827 References

828

829 Afghah, T., Heeren, J., Hartog, L., Biermann, P., Wulff, A., Warzybok, A., & Wagener, K. C. (2025). An open-access dataset of
830 unaided and hearing aid-assisted auditory perception measures in complex virtual acoustic scenes. *International Journal of*
831 *Audiology*, 1-14. DOI: 10.1080/14992027.2025.2601653.

832 Afghah, T., Alfakir, R., Meis, M., Hammady, M., Youssif, M., Kramer, S. E., & Wagener, K. C. (2024). ICF-Based Hearing and
833 Functioning Assessment: Validation and Research Outcomes of Utilizing the HEAR-COMMAND Tool for Patients with Mild to
834 Moderately Severe Hearing Loss and Individuals with Normal Hearing. *Frontiers in Rehabilitation Sciences*, 5, 1389653.
835 doi:10.3389/fresc.2024.1389653.

836 Afghah, T., Alfakir, R., Meis, M., van Leeuwen, L., Kramer, S. E., Hammady, M., ... & Wagener, K. C. (2022). The development
837 of a Self-Rated ICF-based questionnaire (HEAR-COMMAND Tool) to evaluate Hearing, Communication, and Conversation
838 disability: Multinational experts' and patients' perspectives. *Frontiers in rehabilitation sciences*, 3, 1005525.
839 doi:10.3389/fresc.2022.1005525.

840 Afghah T, Wagener KC (2026). A comparative analysis of a perceptual hearing loss assessment database and the International
841 Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health Core Sets for Hearing Loss. [Preprint] Zenodo. DOI:
842 10.5281/zenodo.17085375.

843 Afghah, T., Schütze, J., Meis, M., Kollmeier, B., & Wagener, K. C. (2023). Conformities and gaps of clinical audiological data
844 with the international classification of functioning disability and health core sets for hearing loss. *International journal of audiology*,
845 62(6), 552-561. DOI:10.1080/14992027.2022.2078433.

846 Alfakir R, Hammady M, Afghah T, Abd Al-Ghaffar M, Youssif M.(2025a). Translation, Cultural Adaptation, and Validation of
847 the Arabic Version of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool: A Self-Rated ICF-Based Questionnaire for Assessing Hearing,
848 Communication, and Conversation Disability in Arabic-Speaking Populations. *The Egyptian Journal of Otolaryngology*. doi:
849 10.1186/s43163-025-00832-4.

850 Alfakir R, Dunaway L, Hyun J, Sagong H, Afghah T, Kang S (2025b) Translation, Cultural Adaptation, and Field Testing of the
851 Korean Version of the HEAR-COMMAND Tool: A Self-Rated ICF-Based Questionnaire for Assessing Hearing, Communication,
852 and Conversation Disability in Korean-Speaking Populations. *Journal of Audiology & Otology*, 29(3), 197. doi:
853 10.7874/jao.2025.00136.

854 Bradburn, N. M., Rips, L. J., & Shevell, S. K. (1987). Answering autobiographical questions: The impact of memory and inference
855 on surveys. *Science*, 236(4798), 157-161.

856 Christensen, J. H., Rumley, J., Gil-Carvajal, J. C., Whiston, H., Lough, M., & Saunders, G. H. (2024b). Predicting Individual
857 Hearing-Aid Preference From Self-Reported Listening Experiences in Daily Life. *Ear and hearing*, 45(5), 1313–1325. DOI:
858 10.1097/AUD.0000000000001520.

859 Cherry, E. C. (1953). Some experiments on the recognition of speech with one or two ears. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 22, 61-62.

860 Cox, R. M., & Alexander, G. C. (2002). The International Outcome Inventory for Hearing Aids (IOI-HA): psychometric properties
861 of the English version: El Inventario Internacional de Resultados para Auxiliares Auditivos (IOI-HA): propiedades psicometricas
862 de la version en ingles. *International journal of audiology*, 41(1), 30-35.

863 Cubick, J., & Dau, T. (2016). Validation of a virtual sound environment system for testing hearing aids. *Acta Acustica united with*
864 *Acustica*, 102(3), 547-557. DOI: 10.3813/AAA.918972.

865 Danermark B, Cieza A, Gangé J-P, Gimigliano F, Granberg S, Hickson L, et al., International classification of functioning,
866 disability, and health core sets for hearing loss: a discussion paper and invitation. *Int J Audiol*. (2010) 49(4):256–62. DOI:
867 10.3109/14992020903410110.

868 Danermark B, Granberg S, Kramer SE, Selb M, Möller C. The creation of a comprehensive and a brief core set for hearing loss
869 using the international classification of functioning, disability and health. *Am J Audiol*. (2013). 22(2):323–8. DOI: 10.1044/1059-
870 0889(2013/12-0052).

871 Dillon, H., James, A., & Ginis, J. (1997). Client Oriented Scale of Improvement (COSI) and its Relationship to Several Other
872 Measures of Benefit and Satisfaction Provided by Hearing Aids. *Journal of the American Academy of Audiology*, 8(1), 27–43.

873 El-Toukhy, S., Pike, J. R., Zuckerman, G., & Hegeman, P. (2023). Decision trade-offs in ecological momentary assessments and
874 digital wearables uptake: protocol for a discrete choice experiment. *JMIR Research Protocols*, 12(1), e47567. DOI: 10.2196/47567.

875 Fifield, K., Veerakanjana, K., Hodsoll, J., Kuntsi, J., Tye, C., & Simblett, S. (2025). Completion Rates of Smart Technology
876 Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) in Populations With a Higher Likelihood of Cognitive Impairment: A Systematic
877 Review and Meta-Analysis. *Assessment*. DOI: 10.1177/10731911241306364.

878 Gatehouse, S., & Noble, W. (2004). The Speech, Spatial and Qualities of Hearing Scale (SSQ). *International Journal of audiology*,
879 43(2), 85–99. DOI: 10.1080/14992020400050014.

880 [Gerken, M., Schütze, J., Kirsch, C., Ewert, S. D., Seeber, B. U., Heeren, J., Afghah, T., Wagener, K. C., Kollmeier, B., & Warzybok,](#)
881 [A. \(2026\). Perceptual measures of normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners across defined virtual acoustic scenes.](#)
882 [International Journal of Audiology, 1-33.](#) doi: 10.1080/14992027.2026.2615093

883 Goldberg, R. L., Piccirillo, M. L., Nicklaus, J., Skillington, A., Lenze, E., Rodebaugh, T. L., Kallogjeri, D., & Piccirillo, J. F.
884 (2017). Evaluation of Ecological Momentary Assessment for Tinnitus Severity. *JAMA otolaryngology-- head & neck surgery*,
885 143(7), 700–706. DOI:10.1001/jamaoto.2017.0020.

886 Granberg S. (2015). Functioning and disability in adults with hearing loss: the preparatory studies in the ICF core sets for hearing
887 loss project. [Doctoral dissertation]. Örebro University.

888 Holube, I., von Gablenz, P., & Bitzer, J. (2020). Ecological momentary assessment in hearing research: Current state, challenges,
889 and future directions. *Ear and hearing*, 41, 79S-90S. DOI: 10.1097/AUD.0000000000000934.

890 Howard, A. L., & Lamb, M. (2024). Compliance trends in a 14-week ecological momentary assessment study of undergraduate
891 alcohol drinkers. *Assessment*, 31(2), 277-290. DOI: 10.1177/10731911231159937.

892 Jorgensen, E., Hohmann, V., & Kayser, H. (2025). Investigating complex acoustic environments in individuals' daily lives using a
893 research hearing aid. *Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics*, 56, 050004. DOI: 10.1121/2.0002122.

894 Kahneman, D., Diener, E., & Schwarz, N. (Eds.). (1999). *Well-being: Foundations of hedonic psychology*. Russell Sage Foundation.

895 Kowalk, U., Franz, S., Groenewold, H., Holube, I., von Gablenz, P., & Bitzer, J. (2020). olMEGA: An open source android solution
896 for ecological momentary assessment. DOI: 10.3205/zaud000012.

897 Kraft, R., Langguth, B., Simoes, J., Reichert, M., Schlee, W., & Pryss, R. (2025). Global 10 year ecological momentary assessment
898 and mobile sensing study on tinnitus and environmental sounds. *npj Digital Medicine*, 8(1), 162./ DOI:10.1038/s41746-025-01551-
899 z.

900 Kunchay, S., Linden-Carmichael, A. N., & Abdullah, S. (2024). Using a Smartwatch App to Understand Young Adult Substance
901 Use: Mixed Methods Feasibility Study. *JMIR Human Factors*, 11, e50795. DOI:10.2196/50795.

902 Lelic, D., Parker, D., Herrlin, P., Wolters, F., & Smeds, K. (2024). Focusing on positive listening experiences improves hearing
903 aid outcomes in experienced hearing aid users. *International Journal of Audiology*, 63(6), 420-430. DOI:
904 10.1080/14992027.2023.2190006.

905 Manolov, R., Losada, J. L., Chacón-Moscoso, S., & Sanduvete-Chaves, S. (2016). Analyzing two-phase single-case data with non-
906 overlap and mean difference indices: Illustration, software tools, and alternatives. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, Article 32. DOI:
907 0.3389/fpsyg.2016.00032.

908 Mansour, N., Marschall, M., May, T., Westermann, A., & Dau, T. (2021). Speech intelligibility in a realistic virtual sound
909 environment. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 149(4), 2791-2801. DOI: 10.1121/10.0004779.

910 Newman, C. W., Weinstein, B. E., Jacobson, G. P., & Hug, G. A. (1990). The Hearing Handicap Inventory for Adults: psychometric
911 adequacy and audiometric correlates. *Ear and hearing*, 11(6), 430-433.

912 Parker, R. I., & Vannest, K. J. (2009). An improved effect size for single-case research: Nonoverlap of all pairs. *Behavior Ther-*
913 *apy*, 40(4), 357–367. DOI: 10.1016/j.beth.2008.10.006.

914 Parker, R. I., Vannest, K. J., & Davis, J. L. (2011). Effect size in single-case research: A review of nine nonoverlap techniques.
915 *Behavior Modification*, 35(4), 303–322. DOI: 10.1177/ 0145445511399147.

916 Reis, H. T. (2018). Why researchers should think “real-world”: A conceptual rationale. In *Relationships, well-being and behaviour*
917 (pp. 249-271). Routledge.

918 Robinson, M. D., & Clore, G. L. (2002). Belief and feeling: evidence for an accessibility model of emotional self-report.
919 *Psychological bulletin*, 128(6), 934. DOI: 10.1037//0033-2909.128.6.934.

920 Rizvi, S. L., Ruork, A. K., Yin, Q., Yeager, A., Taylor, M. E., & Kleiman, E. M. (2024). Using Biosensor Devices and Ecological
921 Momentary Assessment to Measure Emotion Regulation Processes: Pilot Observational Study With Dialectical Behavior Therapy.
922 *JMIR Mental Health*, 11, e60035. DOI: 10.2196/60035.

923 Salvago, P., Vaccaro, D., Plescia, F., Vitale, R., Cirrincione, L., Evola, L., & Martines, F. (2024). Client Oriented Scale of
924 Improvement in First-Time and Experienced Hearing Aid Users: An Analysis of Five Predetermined Predictability Categories
925 through Audiometric and Speech Testing. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 13(13), 3956. DOI: 10.3390/jcm13133956.

926 Schinkel-Bielefeld, N., Kunz, P., Zutz, A., & Buder, B. (2020). Evaluation of hearing aids in everyday life using ecological
927 momentary assessment: what situations are we missing?. *American Journal of Audiology*, 29(3S), 591-609. DOI:
928 10.1044/2020_AJA-19-00075.

929 Schlee, W., Pryss, R. C., Probst, T., Schobel, J., Bachmeier, A., Reichert, M., & Langguth, B. (2016). Measuring the moment-to-
930 moment variability of tinnitus: the Track Your Tinnitus smart phone app. *Frontiers in aging neuroscience*, 8, 294.
931 DOI:10.3389/fnagi.2016.00294.

932 Schleicher, M., Unnikrishnan, V., Neff, P., Simoes, J., Probst, T., Pryss, R., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2020). Understanding
933 adherence to the recording of ecological momentary assessments in the example of tinnitus monitoring. *Scientific reports*, 10(1),
934 22459. DOI:10.1038/s41598-020-79527-0.

935 Shiffman, S., Stone, A. A., & Hufford, M. R. (2008). Ecological momentary assessment. *Annu. Rev. Clin. Psychol.*, 4(1), 1-32.
936 DOI:10.1146/annurev.clinpsy.3.022806.091415.

937 Stone, A., Shiffman, S., Atienza, A., & Nebeling, L. (2007). *The science of real-time data capture: Self-reports in health research*.
938 Oxford University Press.

939 Timmer, B. H. B., Hickson, L., & Launer, S. (2018). Do Hearing Aids Address Real-World Hearing Difficulties for Adults With
940 Mild Hearing Impairment? Results From a Pilot Study Using Ecological Momentary Assessment. *Trends in hearing*, 22,
941 2331216518783608. DOI:10.1177/2331216518783608.

942 Tonkin, S., Gass, J., Wray, J., Maguin, E., Mahoney, M., Colder, C., ... & Hawk Jr, L. W. (2023). Evaluating declines in compliance
943 with ecological momentary assessment in longitudinal health behavior research: Analyses from a clinical trial. *Journal of Medical*
944 *Internet Research*, 25, e43826. DOI: 10.2196/43826.

945 van De Par, S., Ewert, S. D., Hladek, L., Kirsch, C., Schütze, J., Llorca-Bofi, J., ... & Seeber, B. U. (2022). Auditory-visual scenes
946 for hearing research. *Acta Acustica*, 6, 55. DOI: 10.1051/aacus/2022032.

947 Vercammen, C., Oosthuizen, I., Manchaiah, V., Ratinaud, P., Launer, S., & Swanepoel, D. W. (2023). Real-life and real-time
948 hearing aid experiences: Insights from self-initiated ecological momentary assessments and natural language analysis. *Frontiers in*
949 *Digital Health*, 5, 1104308. DOI: 10.3389/fdgh.2023.1104308.

950 von Gablenz, P., Kowalk, U., Bitzer, J., Meis, M., & Holube, I. (2021). Individual hearing aid benefit in real life evaluated using
951 ecological momentary assessment. *Trends in hearing*, 25, 2331216521990288. DOI: 10.1177/2331216521990288.

952 World Health Organization. (2021). *World report on hearing*. World Health Organization.

953 Wrzus, C., & Neubauer, A. B. (2023). Ecological momentary assessment: A meta-analysis on designs, samples, and compliance
954 across research fields. *Assessment*, 30(3), 825-846. DOI: 10.1177/10731911211067538.

955

956

957

958

959

960

961

962 Table 1. The Questionnaire administered in phase one through the olMEGA App. If “Not at all
 963 impaired” or “Very little impaired” was selected, the questionnaire automatically terminated.
 964 **For Q5, selecting “Other situations” opened a free-text input page and then terminated the
 965 questionnaire. ***If “No one/Nothing” or “It is quiet” was selected, the follow up questions were
 966 skipped and the questionnaire terminated after Q26, as there was either no intention to listen or no
 967 surrounding sounds.

Overall content	Q #	Question	Response Options
Time since event	Q1	How many minutes ago was the event?	Now/2-3/5/10/15/30 (minutes ago)
Self-perceived hearing impairment degree *	Q2	How much do you feel impaired?	Not at all impaired/very little/Little/Medium/Fairly/very/Extremely impaired
Importance of hearing in the situation	Q3	How important is it to hear well in this situation?	very important/ Important/ rather important/ Partly important/ rather unimportant/ Unimportant/ Completely unimportant
Primary Location **	Q4	Which situation applies?	at home / on the way/ in social settings / at work/ other situations
Secondary Location	Q5	And that was: (In case of "home")	Resting / Eating / Kitchen work / Reading, computer / Listening to music / Housework / Outside: garden, balcony/ Others
	Q8	And that was: (In case of "on way")	Driving a car by yourself/ Carpooling / Bus / Train/ Walking / Bicycle/ Subway station/ Others
	Q11	And that was: (In case of "in social settings")	Visiting someone/ Party/ Restaurant, café / Theater, church, lecture / Meeting / Government office, Doctor’s office / Store, shopping / Others
	Q14	And that was: (In case of "at work")	Office / Workshop / Counter, Service Desk / Meeting room / Outside / Cafeteria, Tea Kitchen / Others
Target Sounds ***	Q6 / Q9 / Q12	Whom or what do you mainly listen to?	Only one person / More than one person / Landline phone / Mobile phone / Hands-free / Loudspeaker / Devices, dishes/

	/		TV or radio (only speech) / TV or radio (others) or music / No one, nothing / It is quiet
Masker Sounds	Q7 / Q10 / Q13 / Q16	What other noises are present besides the ones you are currently listening to?	No other sound / One more person / More than one other person / Landline phone / Mobile phone / Hands-free / Loudspeaker / Devices, dishes, Engine noises / TV, Radio, Music / Natural Sounds (birds, Leaves) / Others
Listening effort	Q17	How tiring/exhausting is it to listen?	effortless / very little effort / little effort / medium effort/ fairly tiring / very tiring / extremely tiring
Concentration difficulty	Q18	How difficult is it to concentrate while listening?	not at all / very little / little / medium / fairly / very / extremely difficult
Speech comprehension	Q19	How good or bad do you understand?	perfect/ very good / rather good/ average/ fairly poor / very poor / not at all
Loudness perception	Q20	How loud is it?	too loud / very loud / loud / medium / quiet / very quiet / too quiet
Pleasantness of sound	Q21	How pleasant are the noises/sounds?	very pleasant / pleasant / fairly pleasant / neutral / fairly unpleasant / unpleasant / very unpleasant
Sound localization	Q22	How well do you hear where do individual sounds come from?	perfect / very good / fairly good/ average/ fairly bad/ very bad/ not at all
Familiarity of sounds	Q23	Are the voices familiar to you? (if applicable)	Familiar / not familiar/ both / not applicable
Immersion in conversation	Q24	Do you feel immersed in conversation? (if applicable)	fully immersed / fairly immersed / sometimes immersed, sometimes left out / fairly left out / not applicable
Conversation difficulty (partner)	Q25	Do you think your conversation partner finds the conversation difficult? (if applicable)	not at all / very little / little / medium / fairly / very / extremely difficult / not applicable
Mood	Q26	What is your current mood? (presented as emojis)	very happy/ happy / neutral / very sad / sad

		HI-noHA:	×1					×1	×2		×3
Live, Speech (Loudspeaker)		NH:									
		HI-ownHA:			×2	×1	×2	×3	×2		×2
		HI-noHA:									
Live, non- speech (Appliances/ Dishes)		NH:	×1					×1			
		HI-ownHA:			×1		×1	×1			×3
		HI-noHA:		×3				×3			
Media devices (TV/Radio Only speech)		NH:	×1	×1					×1		
		HI-ownHA:	×4	×2				×5	×1		×3
		HI-noHA:	×5	×1	×1			×8	×5		
Media devices (TV/Radio Others, Music)		NH:	×2	×1					×1	×1	
		HI-ownHA:	×4	×9				×1	×9	×3	
		HI-noHA:	×4	×5	×4	×2		×2	×8		×2

979

980

981

982

983

984

985

986 Table 3. Hearing aid fitting effect, estimated as phase effects from cumulative-link mixed models
 987 (proportional-odds, logit link) with a random intercept for participants. Estimates are presented as
 988 logit coefficients (β) with 95% confidence intervals (CI). Positive β indicates higher odds of
 989 selecting higher response categories in unaided condition (phase one of study) relative to aided
 990 condition (phase two). Questions are sorted by β from largest to smallest.

Content	Question	β (logit)	95% CI	p-value
Speech comprehension	19	+6.07	[4.86, 7.29]	< .001
Self-perceived hearing impairment degree	2	+5.15	[4.11, 6.19]	< .001
Concentration difficulty	18	+4.55	[3.66, 5.44]	< .001
Listening effort	17	+4.51	[3.60, 5.41]	< .001
Sound localization	22	+3.50	[2.65, 4.35]	< .001
Pleasantness of sound	21	+2.55	[1.86, 3.23]	< .001
Immersion in conversation	24	+2.42	[1.63, 3.22]	< .001
Importance of hearing in the situation	3	-0.39	[-0.98, 0.2]	0.196
Loudness perception	20	-1.50	[-2.16, -0.84]	< .001

991

992

993

994

995

996

997

998

999 **Figures Captions:**

1000 Figure 1. Study flowchart. Timeline of the two study phases. Phase one for all participants: NH:
1001 Normal Hearing participants; HI-ownHA: Hearing-Impaired participants using their own hearing
1002 aids; HI-noHA: Hearing-Impaired participants who did not use hearing aids prior to the study and
1003 received hearing aid. Phase two only for HI-noHA group in aided settings.

1004

1005 Figure 2. Heatmap showing the number of completed questionnaires per primary location. The
1006 number in each cell shows the count of questionnaires. Darker shading represents higher counts.

1007

1008 Figure 3. Phase one outcomes (part one): comparison of challenging listening situations across
1009 groups, presented as distributions of absolute counts. Top: Primary and secondary selected
1010 locations (Q5, Q8, Q11, Q14). Middle: Target sounds (Q6, Q9, Q12, Q15). Bottom: Masker sounds
1011 (Q7, Q10, Q13, Q16). The labels are abbreviated. The full text is provided in Table 2. NH: Normal
1012 Hearing participants (N=4); HI-ownHA: Hearing-Impaired participants using their own hearing
1013 aids (N=7); HI-noHA: Hearing-Impaired participants who did not use hearing aids prior to the
1014 study and received hearing aid (N=9).

1015

1016 Figure 4. Group-level response distributions for self-report measures collected during phase one.
1017 Each bar represents the percentage of responses per category, averaged across individuals within
1018 each group (across-participant mean). The y-axis indicates the percentage of responses per
1019 response category. Left bar: NH: Normal Hearing participants (N=4); Middle bar: HI-ownHA:
1020 Hearing-Impaired participants using their own hearing aids (N=7); Right bar: HI-noHA: Hearing-

1021 Impaired participants who did not use hearing aids prior to the study and received hearing aid
1022 (N=9).

1023

1024 Figure 5. Comparison of questionnaire response distributions between phase one (unaided) and
1025 phase two (aided) across HI-noHA group (hearing impaired participants who received hearing aids
1026 between the phases, N=9). The responses were averaged withing each category, so that each
1027 participant had equal influence. For phase one, only questionnaires with similar target sounds as
1028 completed questionnaires in phase two were included.

1029

1030